

STATUS OF URBAN POVERTY IN INDIA

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Abstract

Urbanization is a natural consequence of economic changes that take place in a country, which contributes to population development. Nearly twenty eight out of every hundred persons in India live in urban areas. Poverty and lack of employment in the villages lead to migration from rural to urban areas. Increasing industrialization in any country has contributed to the growth of new towns. The growth of urban population in India has brought so many problems including poverty. Urban poverty has a serious impact on economic growth in India. The reasons behind urban poverty are improper training of the people, growing population, slower rate of growth of jobs and failure of Public Distribution System (PDS). Urban poverty alleviation is a challenging task before the government. To reduce the urban poverty, state governments have primary responsibility for planning and initiating programmes like the Urban Basic Services for the poor, the Environmental Improvements of Urban slums. It is time to accelerate the efforts to alleviate urban poverty in major states with high levels of urban poverty through effective strategies to address the root causes of urban poverty.

1. Introduction

Almost half of the world population lives in the urban areas and the cities are growing rapidly, both in size and numbers. The trend is especially stronger in the developing world, where the rate of rural to urban migration is very high. The people flock to cities in search of employment and higher standard of living. Globally, the urban population has grown at an average rate of 4.2 per cent in the past two decades. However, the overall population growth in developing countries in the 1960s and 1970s too was almost double of England during the first industrial revolution.

The growth of urbanization during pre-independence period was slow. Urbanization in India has shown its phenomenal growth during post-independence years because of pressure of growing population, rapid industrialization, rural to urban migration and the growing tempo of modernization. As a result new towns are coming up; already existing commercial and industrial towns are expanding to accommodate the continuing influx of the rural population. Due to the influx of population to the cities, which is mainly due to industrialization and progress in trade and commerce, development in transportation and communication and also due to various other reasons a sizeable managerial cadre is required. In developing nations of the world, one or the other new industrial unit is set up almost daily. This increase in urban population has resulted into over-crowding slum formation and urban poverty. Many other grave problems have also cropped up and by more problems are springing up. Urban poverty, which has a serious impact on economic growth in India.

2. Definition Of Urban Area

In Census of India, 2011 two types of towns were identified.

- (i) Statutory towns: All places with a municipality, corporation, cantonment board or notified town area committee etc. so declared by State Law.

- (ii) Census towns: Places which satisfy following criteria:
- (a) a minimum population of 5000;
 - (b) at least 75 per cent of male working population engaged non-agricultural pursuits; and
 - (c) a density of population of at least 400 persons per sq. km.

3. Trends Of Urbanisation In India

The growth of urbanization during pre-independence period was slow. Urbanization in India has shown its phenomenal growth during post-independence years because of pressure of growing population, rapid industrialization, rural to urban migration and the growing tempo of modernization. As a result, new towns are coming up; already existing towns are expanding to accommodate the continuing influx of the rural population. Thus, the census figure of 10.8 per cent of Indian urban population in 1901 had shown a marked increase to 30 per cent in 2011 (Figure-1 & Table-1).

The rate of urbanization varies over time and space. In the earlier part of 20th century, in 1901, the level of urbanization was only 10.8 per cent with only 26 million people in 1827 towns. In 1951, at the starting point of planned economic development, the level was 17.3 per cent with 62 million urban population. The 2011 population census has recorded 377 million urban population which accounts for 30 per cent of 1210 million total population, distributed over 5161 urban agglomerations/towns. Number of total population has increased from 238 millions in 1901 to 1210 millions in 2011. The number of persons living in urban area for every hundred population of the country increased from about eleven to thirty between 1901 and 2011, registering an increase of seventeen per hundred during the time span of a country. When measured in terms of urban-rural ratio, only twelve persons lived in urban areas for every hundred persons living in rural areas in 1901, and this number increased to 41 in rural areas in 2011. Urbanisation in India has been relatively slow compared to many developing countries. The percentage of annual exponential growth rate of urban population reveals that in India it grew at faster pace from the decade 1921-31 to until 1951. Thereafter in 1951-61 it registered a sharp drop. The decades 1961-71 and 1971-81 showed an improvement but

have steadily dropped to the present level at 2.8 per cent. The sharp drop in urban rate during 1951-61 was mainly due to declassification of a very large number of towns during that period.

Table - 1: Population Of India By Residence: 1901-2011

Census Years	Total Population (in million)	Urban Population (in million)	Number of Urban agglomeration/town	Urban Population as percentage of total population (%)	Population per town ('000)	Rural Population (in millions)	Urban-rural Ratio	Per Annum Growth Rate of Urban Population
1901	238	26	1827	10.8	14	212	12	-
1911	252	26	1825	10.3	14	226	12	0.03
1921	251	28	1949	11.2	14	223	13	0.80
1931	279	33	2072	12.0	16	246	14	1.77
1941	319	44	2250	13.9	20	275	16	2.81
1951	361	62	2843	17.3	22	299	21	3.53
1961	439	79	2363	18.0	34	360	22	2.37
1971	548	109	2590	19.9	42	489	25	3.29
1981	683	159	3378	23.3	47	524	30	3.87
1991	847	217	3768	25.7	58	630	35	3.08
2001	1027	285	5161	27.8	65	742	39	2.85
2011	1210	377	7935	30	73	833	41	3.16

Source: Various Census Reports.

4. Million Plus Urban Agglomerations

The 1971 Census introduced the term Urban Agglomeration (UA) which includes the suburban outgrowths of a particular town with that town itself. In 1971 the UAs having population greater than one million each were- Kolkata, Greater Mumbai, Delhi, Chennai, Hyderabad, Ahmadabad, Bangalore, Kanpur and Pune. Thus there were 9 million plus UAs in 1971. The number of million plus UAs rose to 12 in 1981. The new entrants were Nagpur, Lucknow and Jaipur. In the decade 1981-91 Bhopal, Coimbatore, Indore, Kochi, Ludhiana, Madurai, Patna, Surat, Vadodara, Varanasi and Visakhapatnam also joined the category of million plus UAs and thus the number of million plus UAs were 23 in 1991. In the decade 1991-2001, the number of million plus UAs rose to 35. The new entrants were Agra, Meerut, Nasik, Jabalpur, Jamshedpur, Asansol, Dhanbad, Faridabad, Allahabad, Amritsar, Vijayawada and Rajkot. In the decade 2001-2011, the million plus UAs rose to 53.

In the decade 1991-2011 the most spectacular rise was in the population of Delhi which registered an increase of 52 per cent. The population of the four largest urban agglomerations- Mumbai, Kolkata, Delhi, Chennai- registered an increase of 29.9, 19.9, 52.0 and 18.5 per cent respectively in the decade 1991-2011. Taken together, their population rose from 372.24 lakh in 1991 to 487.99 lakh in 2011 registering an increase of 31.1 per cent.

The population of 53 mega-cities was about 38 per cent of the total urban population. Delhi ranked first with a population of 21.7 million, followed by Kolkata with a population of 14.6 million. The population of greater Mumbai 20.7 which was only million in 1991 has jumped to 20.7 million by 2011 showing an increase of 40.8 per cent during the decade. The overall decennial increase in population in 53 mega-cities was about 68 per cent during 1991-2011 decade. The population of large cities is shown in Table-2.

Table-2: Population Of Large Cities

Name of the City	Population in 1991 (in millions)	Population in 2001 (in millions)	Population in 2011 (in millions)	10-yearly increase (Per cent)
Greater Bombay	12.6	16.4	20.7	40.8
Kolkata	10.9	13.2	14.6	21.1
Delhi	8.4	12.8	21.7	52.4
Chennai	5.4	6.4	8.9	18.5
Bangalore	4.1	5.7	8.7	39.0
Hyderabad	4.3	5.5	7.7	27.9
Ahmadabad	3.3	4.5	6.3	36.4
Pune	2.5	3.7	5.0	48.0
Surat	1.5	2.8	4.5	86.6
Kanpur	2.1	2.7	2.9	28.5
Lucknow	1.6	2.2	2.9	37.5
Jaipur	1.5	2.6	3.0	53.3
Nagpur	1.7	2.1	2.5	23.5

Source: Census of India.

5. Urban Poverty In India

Poverty in India is still rampant despite an impressive economic growth. In 1973-74, the urban poor population was 60 million. It increased to 64.6 million in 1977-78, 70.9 million in 1983-84, 75.2 million in 1987-88, 76.3 million in 1993-94, 77.2 million in 1999-2000 and in 2011 it had risen to 81 million. The growth rate of urban population is due to the large-scale shifting of rural population to urban areas due to industrialization, educational centres, means of transportation, natural factors, net rate of urban migration, marriage migration and business.

This steep rate of growth of urban population along with the urban bias in developing countries has brought in its wake problems like population explosion in cities, problem of housing, slum formation, environmental problem, unemployment problem, urban social problems and urban poverty. Urban poverty, which has a serious impact on economic growth in India.

The estimation of poverty in India is based on two critical components. First, information on the consumption expenditures and its distribution across households is provided by the NSS consumption expenditure surveys. Second, these expenditures by households are evaluated with reference to a given poverty line. Households with consumption expenditures below the poverty line are deemed poor. Poverty in India can be defined as a situation only when a section of peoples are unable to satisfy the basic needs of life. The definition and methods of measuring poverty differs from country to country. The Planning Commission estimates the proportion and number of poor separately for rural and urban India at the national and State levels based on the recommendations of the Task Force on 'Projections of Minimum Needs and Effective Consumption Demands'. The Task Force had defined the poverty line (BPL) as the cost of an all India average consumption basket at which calorie norms were met. The norms were 2400 calories per capita per day for rural areas and 2100 calories for urban areas. If the person is unable to get that minimum level of calories is considered as being below poverty line.

India is stepping forward for becoming a country with more urbanized. The recent experiences tell that the urban areas are facing the problem of poverty. The reasons behind urban poverty are as follows:

- 1) Improper Training
- 2) Growing population
- 3) Slower job Growth
- 4) Failure of Public Distribution System.

The biggest cities are growing faster than smaller towns. India's mega-cities have the highest percentage of slum-dwellers in the country. This indicates that as big cities grow even larger, their slums will swell. While slums have become an important place to reach the urban poor, even though all the urban poor do not live in slums. Establishing an appropriate poverty line to monitor changes in income poverty is also difficult. A poverty line should be set which

reflects the income needed to avoid deprivation within each local context. For urban poverty, at the very least it should reflect the income needed not only to purchase sufficient food but also to obtain a secure shelter with adequate quality water, sanitation and garbage collection, to pay for transport and for keeping children at school, and to afford health care and medicines when needed. The ‘non-food’ monetary costs of avoiding poverty are generally higher in urban areas than in rural areas, as access to housing, resources and services are monetized – and usually particularly expensive in larger or more prosperous cities. But very few nations have income-based poverty lines that vary from place to place, reflecting differences in the income needed to avoid poverty. Where there is provision for this, it usually focuses on variations in the cost of food or variations in what the poorest 20 per cent of households spend on non-food items, which is not the same as the income level they need to avoid deprivation.

6. State-Wise Poverty Share In India

As the analysis presented in Table-3 indicates, Maharashtra, closely followed by Uttar Pradesh, and Tamil Nadu, has the largest share of urban poverty, while Kerala has the lowest share in 2011. Urban poverty share of states such as Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab and west Bengal declined during the last decade, while in other states including Bihar, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Orissa, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh, the share increased. In terms of over-all poverty, Uttar Pradesh accounts for one-fifth of the poor people in India with the other states having major share of poverty being Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra.

Table - 3: Percentage Share of Poor Persons for Major States in India

State	Urban				All			
	1983	1993-94	2004-05	2011	1983	1993-94	2004-05	2011
Andhra Pradesh	7.54	9.35	6.89	6.63	5.31	4.89	3.88	9.20
Bihar	6.53	5.99	6.46	7.35	14.64	16.07	16.53	32.59
Gujarat	6.40	6.11	3.18	3.15	3.51	3.47	3.03	16.63
Karnataka	7.25	7.96	8.32	7.86	4.81	4.97	5.02	20.91
Kerala	3.56	2.66	2.22	2.14	3.29	2.48	1.57	7.05

Madhya Pradesh	9.08	10.78	9.82	8.65	8.61	9.45	10.79	31.65
Maharashtra	13.97	15.52	17.08	16.32	9.04	9.71	10.36	17.35
Orissa	2.44	2.51	3.32	3.39	5.70	5.12	6.03	32.59
Punjab	1.72	1.05	0.66	1.16	0.94	0.89	0.70	8.26
Rajasthan	4.48	4.61	5.52	5.65	4.38	4.21	4.42	14.71
Tamil Nadu	11.83	11.08	13.48	12.52	8.47	6.40	6.10	11.28
Uttar Pradesh	15.75	14.55	15.66	14.32	17.42	19.43	20.93	29.43
West Bengal	7.17	6.13	5.62	6.32	9.77	7.59	7.23	19.98
All India	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Sources: NSSO & Planning commission reports for various years.

7. Living Conditions Of The Urban Poor

Urban poverty was easily discernible through lack of security of land tenure, access to affordable shelter and basic amenities, particularly, health, education and social security. Urban poverty was linked to the aspects of social inclusion, city-wide infrastructure and basic service delivery systems, opportunities for skill development and employment, responsiveness of local governance structures and policies and programmes impacting on urban environment, development and management.

The bulk of the urban poor are living in extremely deprived conditions with insufficient physical amenities like low-cost water supply, sanitation, sewerage, drainage, community centers and social services relating to health care, nutrition, pre-school and non-formal education.

“Workers engaged in the urban informal sector form the bulk of the urban poor. Workers in this sector get low wages or if they are self-employed, their income is meager. This implies that their living conditions are low and, if employed, their wages are less than the stipulated minimum wages. There are hardly any regulations on their working conditions and social security is virtually non-existent. A large section of this population consists of low-skilled rural migrants or migrants from smaller towns. Hence, for these people, right from the time of their entry to the city they become a part of the informal sector as they have neither the skills nor the opportunities to enter better-paid and more secure formal sector jobs. They thus move from one

level of poverty, at their place of origin, to another level of poverty, at their destination. At the same time there is a growing section of workers in the formal sector who have lost their jobs and are compelled to work in the informal sector. For these people and their families this change means a reduction in their standard of living and insecure, unregulated employment". People in urban areas are homeless and slum household share deprived of good housing, they do not have access to clean water, they do not have access to hygienic systems of waste disposal (including the sanitary disposal of faeces) and, in general, they live in polluted and degraded environments not suited to human habitation.

8. Urban Poverty Alleviation Programmes

Urban poverty alleviation is a challenging task before the nation which calls for imaginative new approaches. The goal is to adequately feed, educate, house and employ the large and rapidly growing number of impoverished city dwellers. The bulk of the urban poor are living in extremely deprived conditions with insufficient physical amenities like low-cost water supply, sanitation, sewerage, drainage, community centres, health care, nutrition, pre-school and non formal education. The need of the hour is to assist the urban poor by helping them to set up micro-enterprises thereby providing them avenues for enhancement or supplementation of their incomes. Another major area of assistance to the urban poor is provision of funds for housing or shelter up gradation.

9. Conclusions

Urbanization refers to the population of a nation living in urban areas. Urbanization is an indicator of modernization, the sign of growth of economic progress. In the 21st Century, the rate of urbanization is much more in developing countries than in developed countries. According to the Census of India 2011, out of the total population of 1210 million about 377 million live in urban areas. Nearly twenty-eight out of every one hundred persons in India live in urban areas with a considerable size of slum population growing at nine per cent per year. This steep rate of growth of urban population along with the urban bias in India has brought problems like population explosion in cities, slum formation and urban poverty. Urban poverty has a serious impact on economic growth in India.

The recent experiences tell that the urban areas are facing the problem of poverty because of improper training, growing population, slower job growth and failure of public distribution system. Urban poverty was easily discernible through lack of security of land tenure, access to affordable shelter and basic amenities, particularly, health, education and social security. The bulk of the urban poor are living in extremely deprived conditions with insufficient physical amenities like low-cost-water supply, sanitation, sewerage, drainage, community centers and social services relating to health care, nutrition, pre-school and non-formal education.

The proportion of people living below the poverty line in many Indian states is higher in urban areas than in rural areas. Developed states such as Punjab, Maharashtra and Karnataka, and the less developed states like Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan recorded high levels of urban poverty than rural poverty over a period of time. This indicates that economically developed states also could not ensure percolation of benefits to the urban poor.

To reduce the urban poverty, State governments have primary responsibility for planning and initiating programmes in the urban sector, and have been advised to prepare state based urban development strategies. Poverty alleviation is a specific Urban Local Body responsibility. At the state level, State Urban Development Agencies and District Urban Development Agencies exist, and they are responsible for ensuring coordination between different urban development programmes. It is time to accelerate the efforts to alleviate urban poverty in major states with higher levels of urban poverty through effective strategies to address the root causes of urban poverty.

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